

The organisation of medical and performance departments in European elite football teams

```
# Load necessary Libraries  
library(dplyr)
```

```
##  
## Attaching package: 'dplyr'
```

```
## The following objects are masked from 'package:stats':  
##  
##   filter, lag
```

```
## The following objects are masked from 'package:base':  
##  
##   intersect, setdiff, setequal, union
```

```
library(gmodels)      # For CrossTable
```

```
## Warning: package 'gmodels' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
library(DescTools)    # For Cramer's V
```

```
## Warning: package 'DescTools' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
## Registered S3 method overwritten by 'DescTools':  
##   method      from  
##   reorder.factor gdata
```

```
library(readxl)
```

```
Country_by_Country <- read_excel("Country by Country.xlsx")
```

```
## New names:  
## • `No. of Medical Doctors [M]` -> `No. of Medical Doctors [M]...13`  
## • `No. of Medical Doctors [M]` -> `No. of Medical Doctors [M]...26`
```

```
# Ensure your columns are factors
Country_by_Country$Region <- as.factor(Country_by_Country$Region)
Country_by_Country$Structure <- as.factor(Country_by_Country$Structure)

# Create a contingency table
structure_table <- table(Country_by_Country$Region, Country_by_Country$Structure)

# View the table
print(structure_table)
```

```
##
##           0  1  2  3  4
## Eastern Europe  2  1  2  1  1
## Northern Europe  4  5  3  3  3
## Southern Europe  3  7  1  4  8
## Western Europe  2  6  3  5  2
```

```
# Perform the Chi-square test
chi_result <- chisq.test(structure_table)
```

```
## Warning in chisq.test(structure_table): Chi-squared approximation may be
## incorrect
```

```
# Print Chi-square results
print(chi_result)
```

```
##
## Pearson's Chi-squared test
##
## data:  structure_table
## X-squared = 8.9974, df = 12, p-value = 0.7032
```

```
# Calculate Cramér's V for effect size
cramer_v <- CramerV(structure_table)
print(paste("Cramér's V:", round(cramer_v, 3)))
```

```
## [1] "Cramér's V: 0.213"
```

```
# Optional: Detailed cell contribution analysis
CrossTable(Country_by_Country$Region, Country_by_Country$Structure,
           prop.chisq = FALSE, chisq = TRUE, format = "SPSS")
```

```
## Warning in chisq.test(t, correct = FALSE, ...): Chi-squared approximation may be
## incorrect
```

```

##
## Cell Contents
## |-----|
## |                Count |
## |            Row Percent |
## |        Column Percent |
## |            Total Percent |
## |-----|
##
## Total Observations in Table: 66
##
##                | Country_by_Country$Structure
## Country_by_Country$Region |      0 |      1 |      2 |      3 |      4 | Row T
otal |
## -----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----
##                Eastern Europe |      2 |      1 |      2 |      1 |      1 |
7 |
##                | 28.571% | 14.286% | 28.571% | 14.286% | 14.286% | 10.
606% |
##                | 18.182% |  5.263% | 22.222% |  7.692% |  7.143% |
|
##                |  3.030% |  1.515% |  3.030% |  1.515% |  1.515% |
|
## -----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----
##                Northern Europe |      4 |      5 |      3 |      3 |      3 |
18 |
##                | 22.222% | 27.778% | 16.667% | 16.667% | 16.667% | 27.
273% |
##                | 36.364% | 26.316% | 33.333% | 23.077% | 21.429% |
|
##                |  6.061% |  7.576% |  4.545% |  4.545% |  4.545% |
|
## -----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----
##                Southern Europe |      3 |      7 |      1 |      4 |      8 |
23 |
##                | 13.043% | 30.435% |  4.348% | 17.391% | 34.783% | 34.
848% |
##                | 27.273% | 36.842% | 11.111% | 30.769% | 57.143% |
|
##                |  4.545% | 10.606% |  1.515% |  6.061% | 12.121% |
|
## -----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----
##                Western Europe |      2 |      6 |      3 |      5 |      2 |
18 |
##                | 11.111% | 33.333% | 16.667% | 27.778% | 11.111% | 27.
273% |
##                | 18.182% | 31.579% | 33.333% | 38.462% | 14.286% |
|

```



```
library(gmodels)  
library(DescTools)  
  
# Clean column names if needed  
Country_by_Country <- clean_names(Country_by_Country)  
  
# View column names to confirm structure  
names(Country_by_Country)
```

```
## [1] "club_name"
## [2] "league"
## [3] "ranking"
## [4] "country"
## [5] "region"
## [6] "job_title"
## [7] "job_title_other"
## [8] "mens_team_support"
## [9] "womens_team_support"
## [10] "youth_academy_support"
## [11] "other_team_support"
## [12] "years_in_football"
## [13] "no_of_medical_doctors_m_13"
## [14] "no_of_physiotherapist_m"
## [15] "no_of_massage_therapist_m"
## [16] "no_of_nutritionist_m"
## [17] "no_of_psychologist_m"
## [18] "no_of_rehabilitation_coach_return_to_play_specialist_m"
## [19] "no_of_head_of_performance_head_of_sports_science_m"
## [20] "no_of_sports_scientist_load_monitoring_amp_data_analysis_m"
## [21] "no_of_fitness_conditioning_on_the_pitch_athletic_trainer_performance_coach_m"
## [22] "no_of_fitness_conditioning_in_the_gym_strength_and_conditioning_m"
## [23] "no_of_manual_therapist_m"
## [24] "no_of_administrative_assistant_m"
## [25] "no_of_data_analyst_m"
## [26] "no_of_medical_doctors_m_26"
## [27] "no_of_physiotherapist_w"
## [28] "no_of_massage_therapist_w"
## [29] "no_of_nutritionist_w"
## [30] "no_of_psychologist_w"
## [31] "no_of_rehabilitation_coach_return_to_play_specialist_w"
## [32] "no_of_head_of_performance_head_of_sports_science_w"
## [33] "no_of_sports_scientist_load_monitoring_amp_data_analysis_w"
## [34] "no_of_fitness_conditioning_on_the_pitch_athletic_trainer_performance_coach_w"
## [35] "no_of_fitness_conditioning_in_the_gym_strength_and_conditioning_w"
## [36] "no_of_manual_therapist_w"
## [37] "no_of_administrative_assistant_w"
## [38] "no_of_data_analyst_w"
## [39] "total_staff"
## [40] "reporting_line"
## [41] "ceo"
## [42] "sporting_director"
## [43] "president"
## [44] "internally_reporting_to_other"
## [45] "does_an_organisational_structure_exist_within_your_medical_and_performance_department_y
es"
## [46] "does_an_organisational_structure_exist_within_your_medical_and_performance_department_n
o"
## [47] "does_an_organisational_structure_exist_within_your_medical_and_performance_department_n
ot_applicable"
## [48] "structure"
## [49] "flat_structure"
```

```
## [50] "flat_structure_comments"
## [51] "divisional_structure"
## [52] "divisional_structure_comments"
## [53] "functional_structure"
## [54] "functional_structure_comment"
## [55] "matrix_structure"
## [56] "matrix_structure_comments"
## [57] "leadership_model"
## [58] "sd"
## [59] "ho_m"
## [60] "hc"
## [61] "sr"
## [62] "oth"
## [63] "daily_meetings"
## [64] "weekly_meetings"
## [65] "monthly_meetings"
## [66] "never_meeting_formally_only_informal"
## [67] "other_meetings"
## [68] "in_the_case_of_informal_meetings_how_often_do_these_take_place"
## [69] "kt_strongly_disagree"
## [70] "kt_disagree"
## [71] "kt_neither_disagree_nor_agree"
## [72] "kt_agree"
## [73] "kt_strongly_agree"
## [74] "es_strongly_disagree"
## [75] "es_disagree"
## [76] "es_neither_disagree_nor_agree"
## [77] "es_agree"
## [78] "es_strongly_agree"
## [79] "cpd_strongly_disagree"
## [80] "cpd_disagree"
## [81] "cpd_neither_disagree_nor_agree"
## [82] "cpd_agree"
## [83] "cpd_strongly_agree"
```

```
# Inspect unique values
table(Country_by_Country$region)
```

```
##
## Eastern Europe Northern Europe Southern Europe Western Europe
##           7           18           23           18
```

```
table(Country_by_Country$leadership_model)
```

```
##
## 1 2 3 4 5
## 37 8 4 2 15
```

```
# Create contingency table: Region x Leadership Model
contingency_table <- table(Country_by_Country$region, Country_by_Country$leadership_model)

# View the contingency table
print(contingency_table)
```

```
##
##           1  2  3  4  5
## Eastern Europe  3  0  2  0  2
## Northern Europe  7  3  0  1  7
## Southern Europe 17  0  0  1  5
## Western Europe 10  5  2  0  1
```

```
# Chi-Square Test of Independence
chi_test <- chisq.test(contingency_table)
```

```
## Warning in stats::chisq.test(x, y, ...): Chi-squared approximation may be
## incorrect
```

```
# Print the results
print(chi_test)
```

```
##
## Pearson's Chi-squared test
##
## data:  contingency_table
## X-squared = 24.939, df = 12, p-value = 0.01512
```

```
# Optional: Detailed cross-tab with row/column proportions
CrossTable(
  Country_by_Country$region,
  Country_by_Country$leadership_model,
  chisq = TRUE,
  prop.r = TRUE,
  prop.c = TRUE,
  prop.t = FALSE,
  format = "SPSS"
)
```

```
## Warning in chisq.test(t, correct = FALSE, ...): Chi-squared approximation may be
## incorrect
```

```

##
## Cell Contents
## |-----|
## |                Count |
## | Chi-square contribution |
## |                Row Percent |
## |                Column Percent |
## |-----|
##
## Total Observations in Table: 66
##
##                | Country_by_Country$leadership_model
## Country_by_Country$region |      1 |      2 |      3 |      4 |      5 | Row T
total |
## -----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----
##                Eastern Europe |      3 |      0 |      2 |      0 |      2 |
7 |
##                |      0.218 |      0.848 |      5.853 |      0.212 |      0.105 |
|
##                |      42.857% |      0.000% |      28.571% |      0.000% |      28.571% |      10.
606% |
##                |      8.108% |      0.000% |      50.000% |      0.000% |      13.333% |
|
## -----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----
##                Northern Europe |      7 |      3 |      0 |      1 |      7 |
18 |
##                |      0.947 |      0.307 |      1.091 |      0.379 |      2.069 |
|
##                |      38.889% |      16.667% |      0.000% |      5.556% |      38.889% |      27.
273% |
##                |      18.919% |      37.500% |      0.000% |      50.000% |      46.667% |
|
## -----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----
##                Southern Europe |     17 |      0 |      0 |      1 |      5 |
23 |
##                |      1.308 |      2.788 |      1.394 |      0.132 |      0.010 |
|
##                |      73.913% |      0.000% |      0.000% |      4.348% |      21.739% |      34.
848% |
##                |      45.946% |      0.000% |      0.000% |      50.000% |      33.333% |
|
## -----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----
##                Western Europe |     10 |      5 |      2 |      0 |      1 |
18 |
##                |      0.001 |      3.640 |      0.758 |      0.545 |      2.335 |
|
##                |      55.556% |      27.778% |      11.111% |      0.000% |      5.556% |      27.
273% |

```

```

##          |  27.027% |  62.500% |  50.000% |   0.000% |   6.667% |
|
## -----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----
----|
##          Column Total |      37 |      8 |      4 |      2 |     15 |
66 |
##          |  56.061% |  12.121% |   6.061% |   3.030% |  22.727% |
|
## -----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----
----|
##
##
## Statistics for All Table Factors
##
##
## Pearson's Chi-squared test
## -----
## Chi^2 = 24.93864    d.f. = 12    p = 0.01511635
##
##
##
##          Minimum expected frequency: 0.2121212
## Cells with Expected Frequency < 5: 16 of 20 (80%)

```